

A Study on University Students on the Awareness of Edupreneurship with Special Reference to Guwahati City, Assam

Paper Id : 18550 Submission Date : 26/01/2024 Acceptance Date : 01/02/2024 Publication Date : 05/02/2024

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10650072

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/anthology.php#8>

Kavita Gagar

Assistant Professor
Department Of
Accountancy
Gauhati Commerce
College
Gauhati, Assam, India

Puja Jalan

Assistant Professor
Department Of Commerce
Gauhati Commerce
College
Gauhati, Assam, India

Abstract

Educational sector became more smart for entrepreneurs and technological up gradation created latest opportunities for those entrepreneurs. Traditionally, the teaching was confined to the walls of classroom and lucid lecture delivery by the teachers to the students. But during Covid-19, online teaching came into trend. The individual who innovates teaching and learning is called edupreneur and that journey is called edupreneurship. This research is an attempt to get an insight on awareness level of edupreneurship among the students of different universities in Guwahati city and it has been found that the majority students of the universities of Guwahati city are moderately aware about the term Edupreneur and Edupreneurship. It can be suggested that social media is the majority preferable tool to broaden the awareness on edupreneurship among the students and citizens in Guwahati city.

Keywords Awareness; Educational sector; Edupreneur; Edupreneurship.

Introduction

Education is a foundation for a "better future"- Elizabeth Warren

Most of the people in this generation believes that education is a purpose to live for a better future. Education is an ideology that nourishes a youth to seek knowledge, behavior and skills for future utopia.

This concept of new innovation and creativity towards education formed by entrepreneurship is called edupreneurship. It is abundantly evident from the phrase "Edupreneurship" that it is a combination of the word Education and Entrepreneurship. Edupreneurs are entrepreneurs who take on risks to invest in education. An entrepreneur who works within the education sector is called an edupreneur. Mindset consists of our principles and our information. The educator who has that entrepreneurial mindset is known as edupreneur. That individual who innovates teaching and learning is called edupreneur and that journey is called edupreneurship. A new mode of teaching is the foremost plan of this term edupreneurship. Edupreneurship is the new dimension to entrepreneurship. An edupreneur has the capabilities of an entrepreneur such as Innovation, Risk Taking, Confidence and so forth.

In traditional learning, the teacher delivers knowledge to the students in classroom. No third party means is involved and hence the pace of learning is constant. But during Covid-19 pandemic, when all the countries were affected globally especially the education sector, the online teaching came into the trend. Online learning is the process of educating the public at large via the internet. Varied mode of teaching can be used such as one-on-one video calls, group video calls, and webinars at several apps such as Zoom, Google meet and so on. Online learning facilitates teaching from any location (our comfort zone i.e our home) and enroll students from various geographical areas. And hence this can be said that a shift has been witnessed from traditional learning to online learning and that's where Edupreneurship can be said to have a broad scope today.

It can't be denied that over the years there has been drastic development in the current education even though innovations and technologies are required. Today, for preparing various competitive examinations, there are education start-ups which cater to the needs of the people of different age groups such as: Gradeup; Byju's; Unacademy.

In order to define innovative solutions to education models at different levels, new learning methods, multiskilling of the workforce, inclusive education, empowerment, and use of technology to meet the increasing challenges of maintaining India's growth, edupreneurship—or the entrepreneurial spirit—would be essential.

Scholars, academics, and thought leaders continue to be interested in the management of educational institutions and universities since it involves many different types of leadership styles, motivations, etc. There are so many positive developments taking place in the education, public, and business sectors today as well as in non-governmental sector projects throughout the world. The many development projects undertaken by edupreneurs are both thrilling and difficult. The main ingredients that result in high-quality delivery are diligence and tenacity. Every institution or university should make an effort to be innovative in the services it develops, guarantee that it is appropriate for society, and work to slake the thirst for knowledge that draws people to educational institutions. The holy duty and obligation to manage and produce educational resources sustainably for the benefit of mankind in general and their development, in particular, falls to edupreneurs, who are the leaders of society. Edupreneurs are forces for positive change in the economy. As a social entrepreneurial group, edupreneurs have made amazingly positive changes to Indian society. For the sake of the economy, edupreneurship must be maintained and encouraged to expand. When supported, edupreneurs will show to be valuable resources for the economy, enhancing many different facets of it. Edupreneurs unquestionably are agents of change who strive for the betterment of society.

Therefore today's education sector is connected between digital education, teacher training and entrepreneurship. The current education sector has opened larger prospect for aspiring businessman willing to flourish their life as an 'Edupreneur', or 'Education Entrepreneur'. Unfortunately, there are barely any studies or concepts on edupreneurship.

Objective of study

The main objective of this study is to identify the awareness level of edupreneur among the students of different universities in Guwahati and to suggest methods to spread edupreneurship among the universities students of Guwahati city.

Review of Literature

Various authors, academicians, research scholars have conducted research on different aspects of edupreneurship. A few relevant literatures relating to edupreneurship are:

Abreu & Grinevich (2013), this study reveals that as the junior faculty in the Higher Education System is involved more in teaching, research work and other administration activities, they remain packed all the time, so, the senior faculty gets more time to devote in entrepreneurial activities in comparison to the junior faculty. For a successful edupreneurship, experience and knowledge plays a vital role.

Friedman & Silberman (2003), study highlighted that Academic Entrepreneurship deals with detail study of micro and macro level of policies, behavior, technology etc, so that, it becomes a bit easier in commercializing the academic entrepreneurship, that is, edupreneurship in Higher Education Institution.

Chaitra Ramanathan (2006), in the study identifies that self awareness and identity are the two basic things that are missing among the students in the Indian education system, despite of this factors, distinction among the population based on the region, caste etc plays a vital role in the Indian education system which leads to decrease in its standard.

Roeles Henk, Samplonius Raut and Shilpa (2011), in the research paper tried to use entrepreneurship learning in such a way that will lead to change in the behaviour of the population towards entrepreneurship in an edupreneurial environment. This pedagogic helps in adding value in the entrepreneurship learning.

Devasenathipathi, Duraipandian.R, In this paper, the authors tried to focus upon the innovations that could be made in the edupreneurship sector. According to the authors, the educational organizations can be divided into five categories and identified some points for improvement. By pursuing the suggested changes, educational institutions will be more respected and the edupreneurship market will flourish. Based on the current research, the future research work will also include e-learning as an option for edupreneurship with its opportunities and challenges.

Thus, this study shows that many study have been conducted on edupreneurship, but , no such study has been conducted with respect to check the awareness level among the student of Guwahati, Assam. Therefore, this study has been conducted.

Methodology

The study is **descriptive and exploratory** in nature. The study has been conducted among the students of different universities of Guwahati city, Assam. The data has been collected by circulating the questionnaire among the students of different universities. Convenience sampling technique was used to collect the data from the students in Guwahati. Apart from this, the researcher has also taken the help of some secondary sources such as journals, magazines, books, websites etc. The total **sample size** of the study is 108. The collected data and information have been analyzed on the basis of **age, qualification, awareness regarding edupreneur**etc. of the respondents. Percentage method have been used for analysis of collected information.

Analysis

1. Age & Qualification of the Respondents

Table No 1: age of respondents:

Age Qualification (years)&	No. of Respondents	Percentage(%)
18-21 yrs & Graduation (UG)	64	59
22-25 & Post-Graduation (PG)	25	23
26 & Above& Pursuing Doctorate	19	18
Total	108	100

Source: *Field Survey June-July 2022*

Interpretation: From the above, it can be analyzed that majority of the respondents are between the age group of 18-25 years. From the above data, it is can be interpreted that the respondents are either pursuing Under Graduate course or Post Graduate course or Doctorate in Philosophy(PhD). And, the maximum number of respondents are either pursuing undergraduation or post graduation.

2. Awareness About Edupreneurship

Table No 2:the awareness about the term Edupreneurship by the respondents:

Awareness level	No of Respondents	Percentage(%)
Highly aware	24	22
Moderately aware	58	54
Aware	0	0
Moderately unaware	14	13
Highly unaware	12	11
Total	108	100

Source: Field Survey June-July 2022

Interpretation: From the above analysis it is seen that out of 108 respondents, 24 respondents are highly aware about the term Edupreneurship, 58 respondents are moderately aware about the term Edupreneurship, 14 respondents are moderately unaware about the term Edupreneur and 12 respondents are highly unaware about the term Edupreneurship. From the above analysis it has been observed that 22% of the respondents are highly aware about the term Edupreneurship, 54% of the respondents are moderately aware about the term Edupreneurship, 13% of the respondents are moderately unaware about the term Edupreneurship and 11% of the respondents are highly unaware about the term Edupreneurship.

3. Awareness Among the Citizen Regarding Edupreneurship is Poor.

Table No 3: respondents view regarding whether the awareness on Edupreneurship among the citizen is poor:

Awareness level	No. of Respondents	Percentage(%)
Strongly agree	30	28
Agree	52	48
Neutral	17	16
Disagree	9	8
Total	108	100

Source: Field Survey June-July 2022

Interpretation:As per the data collected, majority (48 %) of the respondents agree that the awareness regarding the upcoming entrepreneurship i.e. edupreneurship among the citizen of Guwahati is poor. At the same time, only a few respondents (i.e. 8 %) thinks that the citizen of Guwahati are aware regarding edupreneurship.

4. Source of Spreading Awareness on Edupreneurship.

Table No 4: Showing the source of spreading awareness on Edupreneurship:

Source	No of Respondents	Percentage(%)
Social Media	45	42
Magazine	16	15
Newspaper	31	28
Television	16	15
Total	108	100

Source: Field Survey June-July 2022

Interpretation: From the above, it can be interpreted that as per the respondents, social media is the most preferable media to spread the awareness among the citizens in guwahaticity followed by newspaper, magazine and television.

The major findings of the study can be highlighted as below:

1. It has been found that majority of the respondents are between the age group of 18-26 years and they are either pursuing under graduation or post graduation course and the respondents are moderately aware about the term Edupreneur and Edupreneurship.
2. While interacting with the students of the universities of Guwahati city, it has been found that majority of the respondents agree that the awareness regarding the upcoming entrepreneurship i.e. edupreneurship among the citizens of Guwahati is poor. At the same time, only a few respondentthinks that the citizen of Guwahati are aware regarding edupreneurship.
3. Therefore, the respondents havesuggested that social media is the most preferable mode to spread the awareness among the students as well as citizens in the city.

Conclusion

An edupreneur is an individual who has the comprehension of aeducator as well as a influence of an entrepreneur. With these two features, an edupreneur can create innovative things for the society and especially for the students. As education and technology go hand in hand, an edupreneur creates online courses, videos, webinars and can carry on selling them at the suitable price in the market. The scope of edupreneurship amongst the university students or the youths lies in the fact that this would allow them to make flaccid income.

After the analysis and interpretation of the collected data, it can be concluded that the awareness among the respondents is not satisfying. As edupreneurship is the upcoming new entrepreneurship in the current scenario and so, the citizens should be aware about the advantages, scope and the limitations of the edupreneurship and the various ways through which one can establish a startup as an edupreneur. Therefore, various measures should be adopted to increase the awareness level among the citizen of Guwahati as well as the government should take some initiatives and financial measures too.

With the help of this study, the user of this article will be able to have a knowledge about the new concept that will help them in enhancing the education system with the use of the latest technology, gain attraction of the students towards education through innovation teaching ideas, helps in improving classroom communication between students and teachers and also help in earning for a better livelihood. With the help of this study the user can get the idea that the level of strength that will have to be put on in this area, so that , at one point of time everybody have the idea about edupreneurship in one or the other form. Through edupreneurship, one can become employed by oneself for full time and also can brighten the future generation and show a better path to Rise and Shine.

Suggestions for the future Study

The study shows that the majority students of the universities of Guwahati city are moderately aware about Edupreneur and Edupreneurship. Moreover, it has been observed that the students express their views regarding the awareness on Edupreneur among the citizen as poor. The suggestions that can be put forwarded are as the following:
 i. The first initiative that can be taken to spread the awareness level is by introducing few

topics in the books in the education sector.

ii. Holding seminars and webinars are a good initiative.

iii. Advertisements in television, newspaper should be done to gain the attraction towards the topic.

Use of social media platform is a good idea. Various social media platforms are Instagram, Facebook, Telegram and many more.

iv. Awareness can be spread by speaking about the topic in the public gatherings by the renowned persons.

v. Journals and magazines are also one of the medium to increase the awareness level among the citizen of Guwahati.

vi. Government should take some measures like giving loan to the entrepreneurs.

References

1. Abreu, M. and Grinevich, V. (2013). The nature of academic entrepreneurship in the UK: Widening the focus on entrepreneurial activities Research Policy. Elsevier B.V, 42(2), pp. 408-422

2. Friedman, J. and Silberman, J. (2003). University Technology Transfer : Do Incentives, Management and Location Matter ?, pp. 17-18.

3. Chaitra, Ramanathan. (2006). A CALL FOR CHANGE: TRANSFORMING INDIAN EDUCATION BY CONNECTING ACADEMIC DISCIPLINES TO STUDENT REALITIES, Master's Integrative Project, Teachers college, Columbia University

4. Devasenathipathi, Duraipandian.R, 'Innovation in Entrepreneurship in the Indian Context

5. Liana LĂCĂTUȘ M. and STĂICULESCU, C. (2016). ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN EDUCATION, University of Economic Studies, Bucharest, Romania

6. Fellnhofer, K. Toward a Taxonomy of Entrepreneurship Education Research Literature: A Bibliometric Mapping and Visualization, Educ. Res. Rev. 2019, pp. 27, 28-55.

7. Sirelkhatim, F.; Gangi, Y. Entrepreneurship education: A systematic literature review of curricula contents and teaching methods, Cogent Bus. Manag. 2015, 2, 1.

8. Jardim, J.; Bártolo, A.; Pinho, A. Towards a Global Entrepreneurial Culture: A Systematic Review of the Effectiveness of Entrepreneurship Education Programs. Educ. Sci. 2021, 11, 398